

Phase Space Methods to Visualize Pandemic Data and Models

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Abstract

A novel technique to visualize pandemic (e.g. coronavirus) data and models is presented. In analogy to a complex physics system, the complete phase space for a pandemic consists of all of the variables and their derivatives. We focus on the new cases and new deaths variables. Both of these start out low (typically zero deaths and one or a few cases), rise to maximum values, and then reduce again to zero or low numbers if the pandemic wanes. The approach is illustrated for three cases: China, New York City, and the United Kingdom. In each case, one or more models is given for reference purposes; the computational visualization technique is model independent. This type of visualization of the data also suggests the use of an angle to know where the pandemic is in its cycle (phase or clock angle) and also the path length of the curve in phase space as a measure. Government officials can use this method of visualization in real time to guide decisions about social and economic restrictions. Over 18 other regions of the world (France, Germany, New Jersey, Japan, Korea, etc.) are shown as supplemental figures. Along with the new deaths/ new cases loop in phase space, both a radar plot visualization and the length of the path length are key methods to monitor a pandemic. Our approach to modeling the coronavirus pandemic using a lognormal solution to the differential equations plus noise and primary harmonics is seen to work very well cross the entire spectrum of infection from lowest to highest mortalities.

1. Introduction

The coronavirus outbreak has taken the world by storm leading to serious economic and social upheaval. Fortunately, the pandemic appears to be nearly complete in the far east (China, Japan, South Korea) and waning in other regions (New York City, New Jersey, Germany, Spain, Italy) of the world. The average citizen has been subjected to nearly daily briefings by mayors, governors, presidents, and prime ministers. We present a simple novel phase space approach to visualizing and tracking this and other pandemics. The ideas are based on work done in nuclear phase space dynamics [1] some years ago.

2. Models and Simulations

Early efforts at understanding disease outbreak focus on the simple logistic model, which has two parameters S and r : a saturation population and a growth rate. The equation for this model is taught and used in physics courses: $y = S/[1 + (S-1) e^{-(rt)}]$. The binomial model, which has an infection probability p , may also be used to describe disease outbreaks and evolution. These models, perhaps because of their simplicity, are limited in use and accuracy.

A basic time stepped simulation [1,2] can be used to better describe the data in a region. Again, there are two parameters S and r . S the “susceptibles” is the long term population that becomes infected; r is the growth rate or transmission coefficient. The differential equation that the

computer simulation solves is: $dy/dt = r y (1-y/S)$. The precision of the simulation can be verified by comparison to both exponential growth and logistic model growth, respectively. With a time step of 0.1 day in the simulation, the percent error versus the logistic equation is typically less than 0.1 %.; in all the calculations shown here 0.01 day is used.

To include death and recovery requires a bit more sophistication in the model. The single differential equation is changed to a coupled set of four equations:

$$(1) \frac{dy}{dt} = r y (1-y/S-R/S-D/S) - b y - d y$$

$$(2) \frac{dx}{dt} = -r y (1-y/S-R/S-D/S)$$

$$(3) \frac{dR}{dt} = b y$$

$$(4) \frac{dD}{dt} = d y$$

where y is the number of Infected, x is the number of Susceptibles, R is the Recovered, and D is the Deaths. Note that since $x + y + R + D = S$ a constant, the sum of the above differential equations is zero. The parameters b , d , r , and S must be extracted from experimental data of the pandemic and can be adapted to the situation as the disease spreads. The initial conditions that permit the solution of the differential equations using a fixed time step procedure are that at $t=0$, we have $y = 1$, $R = D = 0$, and $x = S-1$. The basics of this type of modeling were developed over 100 years ago [3] and are still in use today in a variety of contexts. Though details of the models (sometimes called SIR for susceptible, infected, recovered) used by decision makers are not given in briefings, typically this type of model is of use.

The cumulative number of cases $Y=y+R+D$ follows a similar set of four coupled equations. A function which fits the coronavirus case and death data fairly well is the hyperbolic tangent: $Y = 1/2 S (1 + \tanh r(t-m))$ where r is again a growth rate and m is the mean or location variable. This is not surprising since under certain conditions the hyperbolic tangent and logistic function are equivalent and the logistic function is a first approximation.

By straightforward differentiation of the hyperbolic tangent equation and the use of the Pythagorean identity for hyperbolic sine and cosine squared, one obtains

$$(5) \frac{dY}{dt} = 2 r Y (1 - Y/S)$$

which is analogous to equation (1) above. This may be coupled with the below three equations to obtain an alternate differential equation (D.E.) model.

$$(6) \frac{dx}{dt} = -2 r Y (1 - Y/S)$$

$$(7) \frac{dR}{dt} = b y$$

$$(8) \frac{dD}{dt} = d y .$$

Since the cumulative number of cases $Y = y + R + D$, the first equation (5) of this alternate model may also be rewritten as $\frac{dy}{dt} = 2 r Y (1 - Y/S) - by - dy$ which replaces (1) and makes it clear that the condition $y + x + R + D = S$ is satisfied.

We program the simulations in Mathematica [4]; Excel on a personal computer or Pages on a Mac may also be easily used. There is not in most of the cases investigated a significant difference between the phase space results of equations (1) to (4) termed “y D.E.” in the figures versus the the alternate model of (5) through (8) labeled as “Y D.E.”.

See Figure 1 for comparison of Centers for Disease Control and Prevention China data [5] to our time stepped simulation models. These type of simulation models are adaptive in the sense that as the pandemic spreads, the model results improve in accordance with new baseline data. The data used in this paper is from the beginning of May through September 2020. Since the models given here adapt as the data is rolled out in real time, what is important is the phase space visualization method.

3. Phase Space

Our way of interpreting the data or model of the pandemic in a region (city, state, country) is via phase space [1, 2]. Looking at the coupled differential equation models (equations 1 to 4 or 5 through 8), all of the quantities y , Y , D , R , x as well as their derivatives may exhibit interesting behaviour. Plots of dy/dt versus y or new cases versus new deaths give useful information. These orbits in phase space define the scope of the pandemic and allow visualization of both disease spread as well as progress towards the desired end of the pandemic event. Unfortunately, not all of the variables may be readily available in reported statistics.

Since the total number of cases (cumulative Y) as well as the number of new cases - and the corresponding death data - are readily available, we proposed [2] plotting new deaths versus new cases. Examples are shown in Figures 2 and 3 for the United Kingdom and New York City [5-8], respectively. The data may either be viewed as a type of random walk or as smoothed connected

points (Figures 1-3). We use a smoothing interval of 5 days; the actual interval does not matter greatly and the unsmoothed data may also be plotted with the fluctuations if desired.

Either way, the phase space picture amounts to a type of random walk in a nearly contained region of phase space. The trajectory of the random walk or the smoother model data is from pandemic start (1 or a few new cases and new deaths) to finish (0 or few new cases and new deaths). In Figure 1 it is seen how China has completed the phase space orbit as the infection there wound down during March. Another infection can occur or the disease may rebound, but still the phase space visualization plot is useful and may show that.

This type of phase space region display thus allows for the possible near containment of the data into a phase space area where the path to mathematical extinction (pandemic end) can be better seen. The new case data, however, can be somewhat noisy due to small numbers, fluctuations, and reporting issues. Indeed, the reported data is often subject to corrections and even the late reporting or adjustment of data [5-8]. In order to improve that data for visualization purposes, a smoothing over several days may be used (again we use five days). The distributions of mathematical statistics can also aid in data visualization and understanding. Further, the new case and new death data can each be fit by a lognormal, normal, gamma, or other distributions (see Figures 1-3 for the simulation results versus the data for China, New York City, and the United Kingdom). More results are shown in Figures 4 through 15 for other regions of the world. China, Korea, and Japan have completed or nearly completed the phase space orbit and if there is a rebound, it can be seen quickly in the phase space visualization. New York City, New

Jersey, France, Italy, Spain, the United Kingdom, and Germany are also seen to be well on their way to completing the phase space orbit though in Europe some rebound is occurring as of September 2020. Brazil, the U.S.A. as a whole, and the World are in the middle of their phase space evolution.

4. Probability Distributions

Since the number of confirmed cases for a pandemic reaches a maximum as the disease runs its course in a region, pretty much any of the probability distributions from mathematical physics and statistics [9,10] may be used to model or fit the data. It is mainly a matter of a normalization constant and shifting of the distribution by the mean. The cumulative number of cases Y equals S times the cumulative density function (c.d.f.). The rate of change dY/dt equals S times the probability density function (p.d.f.). The four coupled differential equations then are:

$$(9) \quad dY/dt = r(t) = S * \text{p.d.f.}$$

$$(10) \quad dx/dt = -r(t)$$

$$(11) \quad dR/dt = b y$$

$$(12) \quad dD/dt = d y .$$

As in equations (1) to (4) and (5) through (8), the quantity $Y+x = y+x+R+D = S$ is a constant.

These equations may be solved using a time stepped method as used above [1, 2]. Alternatively, the statistical distribution may be fit to the data using standard methods. An equation for $R+D$ may be found when Y is an integrable function by the use of an integrating factor with the equation $d(R+D)/dt = (b+d)y = c (Y-R-D)$.

For New Jersey, the correlation coefficients are .9979 (Lognormal) and .9983 (Weibull). For California the correlations are also pretty good: .9959 and .9970. Correlations for China are .9973 (Lognormal) and .9996 (TANH model). We are correlating the entire time vector of the model distribution with the cumulative cases of the data for all the days of the infection.

Typically there are 150 to 200 values in that time series vector from disease outbreak (1 or 2 first cases at $t=0$) to thousands of cases at disease peak.

Table 1. Correlation coefficients for cumulative confirmed case data versus the lognormal model.

Region	Correlation
World	0.9991
U.S.A.	0.9981
China	0.9973
New York City	0.9991
United Kingdom	0.9966
Germany	0.9995
France	0.9998
Italy	0.9987
Spain	0.9994
New Jersey	0.9979
California	0.9959
South Korea	0.9947

We have examined a plethora of probability distributions seeking those that seem to work best. The Chi-squared and non-central t distribution under and overshoot too much to be of use, but the others work fairly well. The gamma, Weibull and lognormal are found to work the best with correlations of .9930 to .9995, depending on the region of the world. Table 1 gives lognormal model correlations with the data for the cumulative confirmed case data; similar results are found for the deaths data.

5. More Phase Space

The phase space plots (Figures 1 to 15) are suggestive of a nearly elliptical contained region in phase space. This is most easily seen in the normal and lognormal distribution models. The main axis of the ellipse defines an angle. The angle may be found by fitting a line to the data or other methods. The magnitude of the angle relates to the severity of the pandemic in terms of mortality per confirmed cases. This is shown in Table 2 below. Angles from the lognormal distribution reference model are also shown.

In order to better simulate the data our standard lognormal reference model includes both Gaussian noise and primary harmonics, which are present in the data. The noise is easily seen by subtracting smoothed data from the unsmoothed data. The harmonics are seen as bumps in the power spectra of cases or deaths (see Figures 7, 8, and 13). Sometimes the noise washes out or overshadows the harmonics so that they are not easily seen in the cases data.

Table 2. Pandemic phase space (death flow) angle compared to confirmed case mortality rates.

Note that China adjusted their death count upwards in early May; thus a range of mortality is shown. In New York City the range shown depends on whether one counts the “probable deaths” or not.

Region	Phase angle (data)	Phase angle (model)	Mortality rate
South Korea	0.59	1.04	0.024
U.S.A.	1.43	1.54	0.030
China	1.57	1.66	.040-0.055
Japan	1.94	2.81	0.053
Germany	2.02	2.55	0.045
New Jersey	3.96	4.19	0.077
New York City	4.75	4.74	.084-0.109
Spain	6.15	6.82	0.110
Italy	7.92	7.77	0.144
United Kingdom	8.09	8.91	0.155
France	9.47	9.02	0.185

Another potentially useful phase space angle can be obtained by shifting the phase space plots (Figures 1 to 12) to the left so that they are roughly centered about the new deaths axis. The angle obtained from the plotted data then starts at 0 degrees increases to 180 degrees and then goes to 360 degrees as the pandemic traverses its course. This second angle can thus serve as a clock tracking the pandemic from inception to mathematical extinction when the cases and deaths return to near zero. See Figure 15 for an illustration of this visualization technique which

can be used to answer the question: what time is it for the pandemic? When will it be over? At an angle of 180 degrees the time is then noon or 12:00 on a scale of midnight to midnight (0:00 to 24:00).

The path length of the loop in phase space is more of an integral measure of the pandemic progress in a region of the world. Examples of the path length are shown in Figures 9 and 11 for South Korea and Germany, respectively. Figure 15 gives the end loop path length for over 18 regions (cities, states, countries); we have also computed values for USA and the World, but these are off scale and so not shown in the figure. Our approach to modeling the coronavirus pandemic using a lognormal solution to the differential equations plus noise and primary harmonics is seen to work very well cross the entire spectrum of infection from lowest to highest mortalities.

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, we have examined a variety of mathematical approaches to modeling the coronavirus pandemic in real time as it happened. Both the time stepped simulation and probability density function approaches reproduce the data fairly well (over .99 correlations) and allow decision makers to plan in accordance with the progress of the pandemic [11] from inception to end. A novel phase space visualization technique of plotting the number of new deaths versus the number of new cases allows analysts or officials to easily see where the pandemic is in its evolution from case one to maximum and finally fading away (or rebounding).

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*Note that all web links were accessed daily early May through August.

Figure 1. The two simulation methods (equations 1 to 4 and 5 to 8, respectively) are compared to China pandemic data.

New Deaths

— Data

- - - Model (y D.E.)

- · - · Model (Y D.E.)

Figure 2. The simulation model (Lognormal with noise and harmonics) is compared to New York City pandemic data.

Figure 3. The simulation model ((Lognormal with noise and harmonics) is compared to United Kingdom pandemic data.

Figure 4. The lognormal simulation model is compared to France pandemic data.

Figure 5. The lognormal simulation model is compared to Spain pandemic data.

Figure 6. The lognormal simulation model is compared to New Jersey pandemic data.

Figure 7. The lognormal simulation model is compared to U.S.A. pandemic data using a power spectrum of the deaths.

Figure 8. The lognormal simulation model is compared to Japan pandemic data using a power spectrum of the cases.

Figure 9. The lognormal simulation model is compared to South Korean pandemic data using the path length in phase space.

Figure 10. Data for the entire world is compared to a hyperbolic tangent probability distribution model.

Figure 11. Data for Germany is compared to the lognormal probability distribution model using the path length as a measure.

Figure 12. The lognormal simulation model is compared to Italy pandemic data.

Figure 13. The lognormal simulation model is compared to New Jersey pandemic data using the power spectrum of the deaths.

Figure 14. The evolution of the cases of the coronavirus pandemic for New Jersey are compared to several models on a unique radar plot where the angle is that of the path in phase space.

Log (Cumulative Cases)

- Data
- Model (Normal D.E.)
- ◆ Model (Gamma D.E.)
- * Model (Lognormal D.E.)

Figure 15. The loop path length is compared to that in the lognormal model for some 18 states and countries (Hungary, South Korea, Japan, China, France, New Jersey, Germany, New York City, Italy, Georgia, Spain, the United Kingdom, New York, Texas, California, Florida, Mexico, Brazil, and India).

